

A Study of the Complex Compounds of N-Benzenesulphonyl Glycines with Some Metal Ions : Part XIX.

N-N'-Dibenzenesulphonyl L-Cystine and N-Benzenesulphonyl L-Cysteine

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A few complex compounds of groups IB and IIB metals have been prepared with the ligands N-N'-dibenzenesulphonyl L-cystine and N-benzenesulphonyl L-cysteine. Attempts have been made to assign their probable structures with the aid of magnetic data, electronic and i.r. spectral data. Similar structural studies have been made on the Cu(II) complexes of the ligand N-p-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine reported earlier.

IN an earlier communication¹ the preparation and properties of the ligand N-p-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine (R^mH_2) and some of its metal complexes have been reported. In the present communication similar studies have been undertaken using the ligands N-N'-dibenzenesulphonyl L-cystine (DBSC or R^dH_4) and N-benzenesulphonyl L-cysteine (NBSC or R^dH_3). Metal derivatives isolated in the pure state are $K_2(R^dH_3)2H_2O$, $Cu(R^dH_2)$, $K_2(Cu(R^d))$ with the ligand (DBSC); and $K(R^mH_2)$, $Zn(R^dH)2H_2O$ and $Cd(R^dH)$ with the ligand (NBSC).

Various physico-chemical properties of the ligands and their metal derivatives have been studied. Some such studies on $Cu(R^mH)_2$ and $BaCu(R^m)_2$ have also been made and included in this paper.

Experimental

The ligands DBSC, NBSC and $R^mH_2.HCl$ have been prepared and purified by following usual procedure^{1,2}. Their metal derivatives have been prepared as stated below.

$K_2(R^dH_3)2H_2O$: To an ethanolic solution of DBSC (R^dH_4) (1.1 moles) an ethanolic solution of KOH (2 moles) was added with stirring. $K_2(R^dH_3)2H_2O$ separated immediately as a semisolid mass which solidified on cooling in an ice-water bath. The compound was filtered, washed well with ethanol,

dried in a desiccator over H_2SO_4 . Analytical results are stated in Table 1. $K_2(R^dH_3)2H_2O$ is hygroscopic and is highly soluble in water.

$Cu(R^dH_2)$: To an aqueous solution of DBSC (R^dH_4) (1.1 moles) in NaOH (2.2 moles), a solution of Cu(II) sulphate (1 mole) was added with stirring. A bright green precipitate separated, was filtered, washed well with water, dissolved in ethanol, filtered and kept open at room temperature. $Cu(R^dH_2)$ separated as bright green crystals. The crystals were collected, washed with ethanol, air dried and analysed. Results are stated in Table 1. It is soluble in ethanol, acetone, dioxan, DMF and DMSO, but insoluble in water.

$K_2Cu(R^d)$: An ethanolic solution of $Cu(R^dH_2)$ (1 mole) was treated with an ethanolic solution of KOH (2 moles) with stirring. The solution assumed a deep blue colouration. The deep blue solution was evaporated in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 and solid KOH. $K_2Cu(R^d)$ separated as deep blue crystalline solid. The crystals were collected, washed with ethanol, air dried and analysed. Results are stated in Table 1. It is soluble in water giving a deep blue solution and its aqueous solution is unstable.

$K(R^dH_2)$: To an ethanolic solution of NBSC (R^dH_3) (1.1 moles) was added an ethanolic solution of KOH (1 mole) with stirring, the pH of the solution was adjusted to $\approx 7.5-8.0$, the mixture was cooled in an ice-water bath. The first crop was filtered out. The mother liquor was evaporated in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 and solid KOH. White shining crystals of $K(R^dH_2)$ separated, the crystals were collected, washed with ethanol, air dried and analysed. Results are stated in Table 1. $K(R^dH_2)$ is highly soluble in water.

$Zn(R^aH)2H_2O$: To an aqueous solution of NBSC (R^aH_3) (1 mole) a solution of Zn(II) sulphate (1.1 moles) was added and the pH of the solution was adjusted to $\approx 4-5$ by adding a dilute solution of NaOH. $Zn(R^aH)2H_2O$ separated as white powder, filtered, washed with water, finally with ethanol, air dried and analysed. Results are stated in Table 1. It is sparingly soluble in water but soluble in dioxan.

$Cd(R^aH)$: To a solution of NBSC (R^aH_3) (1.1 moles) in (1 : 1) aqueous-dioxan was added a solution of Cd(II) also in (1 : 1) aqueous-dioxan, pH of the solution was adjusted to $\approx 3.5-4.0$ by adding a dilute solution of NaOH in the same solvent. $Cd(R^aH)$ separated as white powder, was filtered, washed with water and finally with (1 : 1) aqueous-dioxan, air-dried and analysed. Results are stated in Table 1. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone and dioxan.

Magnetic moments of the Cu(II) complexes have been measured at room temperature and the μ_{eff} values after diamagnetic corrections³ have been recorded in Table 1.

Electronic absorption spectra of the ligands and their salts in water have been recorded; electronic spectra of the Cu(II) complexes of DBSC and R^mH_2 have been recorded in a number of solvents as well as in mull by means of an UVISPEK spectrophotometer at room temperature. Data are stated in Table 2. In the case of mull spectra, values are noted as O.D. in arbitrary units and are shown in parentheses.

I.R. spectra of the ligands, their K-salts and metal complexes have been recorded in KBr matrices and tentative assignments^{4,5} of some important vibrations have been made. Data are stated in Tables 3(a) and 3(b).

TABLE 1. ANALYTICAL RESULTS OF THE METAL DERIVATIVES AND THE MAGNETIC DATA OF COPPER(II) COMPOUNDS

Compounds	Metal %		Nitrogen %		Temperature °K	μ_{eff} in B.M.
	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.		
$K_2(R^aH_2)2H_2O$	12.33	12.37	4.45	4.43		
$Cu(R^aH_2)$	10.85	10.92	4.84	4.82	303	1.88
$K_2Cu(R^d)$	9.71 (K: 11.90)	9.86 (11.89)	4.25	4.26	303	2.03
$K(R^aH_2)$	13.06	13.07	4.70	4.78		
$Zn(R^aH)2H_2O$	18.11	18.13	3.87	3.89		
$Cd(R^aH)$	30.26	30.18	3.72	3.73		

TABLE 2. ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE LIGANDS AND THEIR COPPER (II) COMPLEXES

Concentration : (0.10 mM-0.02 mM for uv spectra in solution)
(10.0 mM 2.00 mM for d-d spectra in solution)

Species	Medium or solvent	λ_{max} (nm)	log ϵ	Species	Medium or solvent	λ_{max} (nm)	log ϵ
$DBSC(R^aH_4)$	EtOH	272	3.20	$NBSC(R^aH_3)$	Water	266	3.11
		266	3.30			259	3.08
		260	3.26			221	3.91
		224	4.15				
R^aH_4 + two eqv. of NaOH	EtOH	266	3.43	R^aH_3 + one eqv. of NaOH	Water	266	3.09
		260	3.39			260	3.03
		221	4.27			222	3.94
$Cu(R^aH_2)$	DMSO	785	1.96	R^aH_3 + two eqv. of NaOH	Water	266	3.16
		380(sh)	2.54			260	3.13
			222			3.96	
	EtOH	760	1.78	$Cu(R^mH)_2$	DMSO	780	1.96
		340(sh)	2.58			400(sh)	2.62
		244(sh)	3.92		DMF	710	1.90
		218	4.02			390(sh)	2.56
	DMF	750	1.89	Mull	700(sh)	(1.13)	
		370(sh)	2.43		560	(1.41)	
$Cu(R^aH_2)$ + two eqv. of NaOH	EtOH	650	1.96	$Cu(R^mH)_2$ + two eqv. of NaOH	Water	670	1.73
		350(sh)	2.98			340(sh)	2.60
		244	4.09			260	4.54
		217	4.15			210	4.49
$K_2Cu(R^d)$	Mull	670	(0.71)	$BaCu(R^m)_2$	Mull	700(sh)	(1.11)
						570	(1.23)
						400	(1.73)

sh = shoulder.

TABLE 3(a). I.R. SPECTRAL DATA OF THE LIGANDS AND THEIR POTASSIUM SALTS IN KBR MATRICES.

R^dH_4	Frequency (cm^{-1})					Tentative Assignments
	$K_2(R^dH_2)2H_2O$	R^dH_4	$K(R^mH_2)$	$R^mH_2 HCl$	$KR^mH.KCl$	
3252(s)	3333- 2740(m)	3257- 3175(vs)	3333- 3030(m)	3295(m)	3279(m)	} O-H, N-H, C-H, NH_3^+ stretches.
		3077- 2857(s)		3200- 2750(m)		
1754(vs)		2597(m)	2532(w)			S-H stretches
		1724(vs)		1748(vs)		Due to -COOH group
	1613(vs)		1575(vs)		1613(s)	COO ⁻ antisym. stretches.
	1399(s)		1408(m)		1399(vs)	COO ⁻ sym. stretches
1333(vs)	1333(vs)	1342(vs)	1342(vs)	1330(vs)	1333(vs)	-SO ₂ N < antisym. stretches
1160(vs)	1163(vs)	1163(vs)	1163(vs)	1162(vs)	1163(vs)	-SO ₂ N < sym. stretches
				1120(vs) 1100(vs)		NH_3^+ rocking
763(s)	758(s)	763(s)	757(s)			C-S stretches.

TABLE 3(b). I.R. SPECTRAL DATA OF METAL COMPLEXES IN KBR MATRICES.

$Cu(R^dH_2)$	Frequency (cm^{-1})					Tentative assignments
	$K_2Cu(R^d)$	$Zn(R^mH)2H_2O$	$Cd(R^mH)$	$Cu(R^mH)_2$	$BaCu(R^m)_2$	
3226(m)		3226(m)	3175(m)	3305- 3295(vs)	3279(m)	N-H, C-H, stretches
				3000- 2690(vs)		NH_3^+ sym. and anti-sym. stretches.
1587(vs)	1587(vs)	1569(s)	1575(s)	1620- 1600(vs)	1600(vs)	COO ⁻ antisym. stretches.
				1580(vs) 1505(m)		} NH_3^+ bending
1389(s)	1393(m)	1389(m)	1389(m)	1410(vs)	1389(m)	
1304(s-br)	1266(vs)	1325(m)	1316(m)	1320(vs) 1305(s)	1258(m) η	-SO ₂ N < antisym. stretches.
1163(vs)	1136(vs)	1156(s)	1156(s)	1165(vs) 1130(vs)	1149(vs)	-SO ₂ N < sym. stretches
				1120(s) 1100(vs)		NH_3^+ rocking
758(m)	757(m)	757(m)	757(m)			C-S stretches

vs = very strong; s = strong; br = broad; m = medium; and w = weak.

Discussion

Magnetic moments (μ_{eff} values) of Cu(II) complexes are found to be in the range 1.82-2.03 BM, at room temperature. Though the μ_{eff} values are in the normal range it is not possible to decide the stereochemistry of Cu(II) from magnetic data only.

The d-d spectra of Cu(II) complexes, show characteristic absorption bands in the region 900-600 nm⁶.

In the case of $Cu(R^mH)_2$ the absorption maxima at 560 nm in the mull spectra shifts to higher wave lengths (red shifts) 710 nm and 780 nm in DMF and DMSO respectively. ϵ_{max} value of $Cu(R^mH)_2$ in both the solvents support distorted octahedral structure⁷. These red shifts of the d-d bands of $Cu(R^mH)_2$ indicate that DMSO and DMF are stronger co-ordinating axial ligands than any axial intra or intermolecular interactions in $Cu(R^mH)_2$. It is clear

that the position of these bands is a useful indication of degree of tetragonal distortion⁸, supporting a square planar or much greater tetragonally distorted structure of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$. The distortion is still more in the anion $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2^{2-}$ as is evident from the position of the d-d band of $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$ in two equivalents of aqueous NaOH. The d-d band of $\text{BaCu}(\text{R}^m)_2$ in the mull spectra also suggests a similar situation.

Regarding the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^d\text{H}_2)$, the d-d absorption maxima at 740 nm in the mull spectra has been found to be shifted to higher wave lengths in its solution spectra in various solvents. From the

position of the d-d bands of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^d\text{H}_2)$ the degree of tetragonal distortion due to the solvents may be arranged in the order $\text{DMSO} < \text{EtOH} < \text{DMF} < \text{Intra or intermolecular interactions in } \text{Cu}(\text{R}^d\text{H}_2)$. However, in the solution spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^d\text{H}_2)$ in two equivalents of ethanolic NaOH, shift to lower wave lengths has been observed and the same has also been found in the mull spectra of $\text{K}_2\text{Cu}(\text{R}^d)$, supporting much more tetragonally distorted structure of the anion $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^d)^{2-}$ than that of the conjugate acid $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^d\text{H}_2)$.

The i.r. spectral data show marked shifts in the band $1754\text{--}1724\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ligands) to lower frequencies in the complexes indicating the presence of M-O bonds. The shifts in the $(-\text{SO}_2\text{N} <)$ stretching frequency at $1342\text{--}1320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ligands) to lower frequency region in complexes support the presence of M-N bonding. The appreciable shifts of this $(-\text{SO}_2\text{N} <)$ band to much lower frequencies at $1266\text{--}1258\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\text{BaCu}(\text{R}^m)_2$ and $\text{K}_2\text{Cu}(\text{R}^d)$ are associated with the ionisation of the imido-hydrogen of the sulphonimido group, as closely comparable shifts have also been observed in the complexes formed by the ligands N-p-toluenesulphonyl glycine⁹ and 2-benzenesulphonamido-methyl benzimidazole¹⁰. However, the shifts in this band from 1333 cm^{-1} ($\text{R}^m\text{H}_2\cdot\text{HCl}$) to 1320 cm^{-1} in $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$ show that imido-hydrogens are still present in the latter, while the band at 1305 cm^{-1} in $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$ is indicative of ionisation of the imido-hydrogens. The bands due to (NH_3^+) stretching, bending and rocking are found in the ligand $\text{R}^m\text{H}_2\cdot\text{HCl}$ and in the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H}_2)$, while they are found absent in $\text{K}(\text{R}^m\text{H})\cdot\text{KCl}$ and $\text{BaCu}(\text{R}^m)_2$. These suggests $\text{R}^m\text{H}_2\cdot\text{HCl}$ to exist as $(\text{R}^m\text{H}_2)^+\text{Cl}^-$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H}_2)$ a structure having the (NH_3^+) grouping. From these considerations it may

be concluded that $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$ exists as an equilibrium mixture of species represented by structures (I) and (II) as shown below.

If the complexes are distorted octahedral there are likelihood of intra or intermolecular interactions. The shifts in the $(-\text{SO}_2\text{N} <)$ stretching frequency from 1160 cm^{-1} (ligand) to lower frequencies $1147\text{--}1136\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\text{BaCu}(\text{R}^m)_2$ and $\text{K}_2\text{Cu}(\text{R}^d)$ indicate such interactions through an O atom of the $(-\text{SO}_2\text{N} <)$ groups. The shifts in this band to 1156 cm^{-1} in $\text{Zn}(\text{R}^n\text{H})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{R}^n\text{H})$ suggests the existence of such interactions, but to a smaller extent. The i.r. spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$ show two bands, one at 1165

cm^{-1} and another at 1130 cm^{-1} . These once again suggest that the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$ exist in an equilibrium mixture of two structures, in one there is no such interactions while in other there is definitely some interactions. The absence of (S-H) stretching frequency at $2597\text{--}2532\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ligand) in the complexes $\text{Zn}(\text{R}^n\text{H})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{R}^n\text{H})$ are indicative of M-S bonding in these complexes.

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